

The Effect of Dietary Supplementation with Different Levels of Grape Seed Oil on Growth Performance and Carcass Parameters in Quails

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of dietary supplementation with different levels of grape seed oil (GSO) on growth performance, feed conversion ratio (FCR), carcass characteristics, and internal organ weights in quails. A total of 400 mixed-sex Japanese quail chicks (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) at three days of age were randomly assigned to four main groups (100 birds each), with each leading group further divided into five subgroups of 20 chicks. During the experimental period, GSO supplementation did not have a statistically significant effect on feed intake (FI) ($p>0.05$). However, in specific periods (particularly at 0.1% and 0.2% supplementation levels), significant improvements in FCR and average daily gain (ADG) were observed ($p<0.05$). Notably, during the early growth phase (days 1–21), GSO supplementation led to a significant increase in ADG. Regarding carcass characteristics, only the dorsal region weight showed a significant increase at the 0.1% GSO level ($p<0.05$). In terms of internal organ weights, significant differences were detected only in heart and proventriculus weights, while no statistically significant differences were found in other organs or abdominal fat percentage. The improvements in growth performance, digestive efficiency, and oxidative balance are believed to be linked to the linoleic acid and phenolic compounds present in GSO. In conclusion, low levels of GSO supplementation may enhance early growth performance and feed efficiency in quails, while its long-term effects are limited.

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1. Introduction

Antibiotics have been used globally for many years as feed additives to enhance animal productivity and to meet the growing global demand for animal-derived protein sources. In poultry production, antibiotics, enzymes (Irmak et al., 2024a), and phytobiotics have been employed to improve growth performance and reduce production costs by preventing infections caused by various pathogenic microorganisms (Hafez, 2011; Basiouni et al., 2023; Azizi et al., 2024; Irmak et al., 2024b). However, the uncontrolled use of antibiotics has been found to contribute to antimicrobial resistance, posing significant risks to both animal and human health. As a result, the use of antibiotics as growth promoters in poultry diets has been banned in European countries and Türkiye (Tuncer, 2007; Abdel-Moneim et al., 2020; Bartkiene et al., 2020). Following the prohibition of antibiotics as feed additives for growth promotion in poultry, researchers have increasingly focused on alternative natural feed additives, such as phytobiotics (Irmak et al., 2024b), resulting in a growing body of research in this area (Aminullah et al., 2025). Medicinal and aromatic plants, as well as their derivatives, have been used since ancient times in both humans and animals for therapeutic and supportive treatment of medical conditions, to promote well-being, suppress unpleasant odors, and enhance the sensory properties of food, feed, and beverages (Göktaş and Gıdık, 2019). The inclusion of plant-derived additives in animal diets has demonstrated beneficial effects on the digestive system and growth performance due to their bioactive compounds with antioxidant and antimicrobial properties (Özbudak, 2019; Foss et al., 2022; Tufan et al., 2023). Essential oils, in particular, contain active components that strongly inhibit pathogenic microorganisms in the intestines, supporting the development of a favorable gut microflora and enhancing overall health (Abd El-Ghany and Ismail, 2014; Du et al., 2016; Özbudak, 2019). Moreover, aromatic plants are known for their antioxidant properties, which help strengthen the immune system, and their extracts are considered natural and safe

(Özbudak, 2019). One such natural plant-derived additive is grape seed. Grape seed is a by-product formed during various grape processing activities, and its oil is typically obtained either by using organic solvents or through mechanical methods. On a dry matter basis, grape seeds contain approximately 8–20% oil; however, the yield of this oil can vary depending on the extraction method, solvent type, processing conditions, grape cultivar, and environmental factors such as harvest year (Garavaglia et al., 2016). Interest in grape seed oil has increased due to its biologically active components, including phenolic compounds, vitamin E, unsaturated fatty acids, and phytosterols (Garavaglia et al., 2016). Grape seed oil contains both hydrophilic and lipophilic compounds. The hydrophilic fraction comprises antioxidant phenolics such as flavonoids, carotenoids, phenolic acids, tannins, and stilbenes, whereas linoleic acid dominates the lipophilic fraction, accounting for 66.0–75.3% of the total fatty acids (Lutterodt et al., 2011; Duba and Fiori, 2015; Rombaut et al., 2015). Reactive oxygen species (ROS) play a crucial role in cell signaling and immune function; however, elevated ROS levels can lead to oxidative stress, which is linked to various diseases. Phenolic compounds derived from grape seed oil, such as resveratrol and quercetin, help mitigate oxidative stress through their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties (Xia et al., 2010). Grape seed oil and its active compound resveratrol exhibit antimicrobial activity, particularly against *Escherichia coli*, and may serve as potential alternatives or adjuncts to antibiotics. Grape seed oil has demonstrated antimicrobial properties by exerting toxic effects on specific pathogens (Dabetic et al., 2020). In particular, it has been shown to inhibit the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *E. coli* (Rotava et al., 2009; Subramanian et al., 2014). Resveratrol exhibits antimicrobial effects by inducing oxidative damage to bacterial membranes, which may support the efficacy of antibiotic therapies (Subramanian et al., 2014). In a study by Ding et al. (2022), where oxidative stress was induced in chickens using tert-butyl

hydroperoxide, resveratrol was found to alleviate performance loss, protect intestinal and ovarian health, and suppress inflammation. Similarly, Tekeli et al. (2014) reported that the inclusion of 15 g kg⁻¹ grape seed oil in the diet improved feed conversion ratio and had a significant quadratic effect on carcass yield. For many years, synthetic antioxidants have been incorporated into animal feeds. However, growing concerns over the safety of these compounds have led researchers to focus on identifying and evaluating natural antioxidant sources (Turcu et al., 2021). Due to its antioxidant, antibacterial, and antifungal properties, grape seed oil has the potential to influence growth performance and carcass characteristics in quail. This study aims to

investigate the effects of grape seed oil, enriched with phenolic compounds and antioxidant properties, on growth performance and carcass parameters in quail.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Animal material and experimental design

In this study, a total of 400 unsexed Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) chicks, each three days old, were used as the animal material. The chicks were randomly assigned to four main groups, each consisting of 100 birds. Each leading group was further subdivided into five replicates, each containing 20 chicks.

Table 1. Composition and nutrient content of the basal diet used throughout the experiment (on a dry matter basis, %)¹

Feed composition	Proportion (%)
Yellow corn	43.39
Wheat	9.50
Wheat bran	1.29
Vegetable oil ¹	3.00
Sunflower meal (32% CP)	6.00
Cottonseed meal (32% CP)	6.50
Soybean meal (48% CP)	27.13
Dicalcium phosphate	0.75
Limestone	1.29
Salt	0.35
Vitamin-mineral premix*	0.25
L-lysine	0.30
L-threonine	0.25
Nutrient composition (%)	
Dry matter %	89.80
Crude protein %	22.60
Metabolizable energy (kcal kg ⁻¹)**	2930
Calcium	0.80
Phosphorus	0.31
Crude fat	4.70
Crude fiber	4.97
Crude ash	5.91
DL-methionine	0.75
L-lysine	1.34
L-threonine	1.05

¹ The same basal diet was used in all groups. Grape seed oil was added to the experimental diets at levels of 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3% as a replacement for vegetable oil.

* Per kg of diet: 13,000 IU vitamin A, 3,500 IU vitamin D3, 100 mg vitamin E, 3 mg vitamin K3, 3 mg vitamin B1, 8 mg vitamin B2, 6 mg vitamin B6, 30 mg vitamin B12, 30 mg niacin, 8 mg calcium-D-pantothenate, 2 mg folic acid, 70 mg vitamin C, 70 mg D-biotin, 200 mg choline chloride, 2 mg canthaxanthin, 0.75 mg apo-carotenoic acid ester, 120 mg Mn, 100 mg Zn, 90 mg Fe, 16 mg Cu, 1.5 mg I, 0.75 mg Co, 0.30 mg Se.

** Calculated based on the NRC (1994) standard table values.

Chicks were assigned to groups based on their average body weights to ensure uniformity among treatment groups. Throughout the experimental period, the birds were fed a standard starter diet formulated for the initial growth phase, containing 22.60% crude protein (CP) and 2930 kcal kg⁻¹ metabolizable energy (ME). The experimental groups included a Control Group fed only the basal diet, and three treatment groups in which grape seed oil was added to the basal diet at levels of 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3%, respectively. Environmental temperature was regularly monitored during the experiment, and continuous lighting (24 hours) was applied. Feed and water were provided *ad libitum* throughout the study. The experiment was initiated when the chicks were 3 days old and continued for a duration of 35 days, until they reached 38 days of age. At the end of the experiment, 20 chicks were randomly selected and slaughtered from each group for carcass evaluation. Cold carcass weights were recorded after the carcasses were chilled at 4°C for 24 hours. At the beginning of the experiment, the initial body weights of the chicks were recorded. Throughout the trial, body weights were monitored weekly through regular weighings. The difference between weekly body weight measurements was divided by the number of individuals and days to calculate the average ADG. Additionally, weekly net feed intake was determined by considering the amount of feed offered and the feed refusals. Based on these data, the FCR was calculated using daily feed intake and daily weight gain.

2.2. Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using Minitab Statistical Software version 22 to determine the differences among the experimental groups. The study consisted of four different groups, each with five replicates. After assessing the normality of the data using the Shapiro-Wilk test, comparisons among the groups were made using one-way analysis of variance (One-Way ANOVA). For variables showing significant differences in the

ANOVA, the differences between group means were identified using Tukey's multiple comparison test. Data are presented as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM), and a significance level of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

3. Results and Discussion

This study investigated the effects of different levels of GSO supplementation in quail diets on growth performance, internal organ weights, and carcass characteristics. During the experimental period (days 1–35), no statistically significant differences were found in total FI between the GSO-supplemented groups and the control group ($p > 0.05$; Table 2). The average FI throughout the entire period was 17.01 ± 1.56 g day⁻¹ in the control group, while it was recorded as 16.71 ± 1.56 , 16.87 ± 1.55 , and 17.14 ± 1.57 g day⁻¹ in the groups supplemented with 0.1%, 0.2%, and 0.3% GSO, respectively (Table 2). Similarly, during the sub-periods of days 1–7, 8–14, 15–21, 22–28, and 29–35, there were no statistically significant differences among the groups in terms of FI ($p > 0.05$). Abu Hafsa and Ibrahim (2018) also reported no differences in FI in their study. Turcu et al. (2021) similarly found no statistically significant differences in FI among groups in their study involving grape seed oil supplementation. Vlaicu et al. (2017) reported that there were no significant differences in average FI between groups fed diets containing control, 2.5% grape seed oil, and 2.5% rosehip oil during days 14–42. The absence of significant differences in total feed intake among the groups suggests that GSO does not have a direct effect on appetite but may enhance feed utilization efficiency. This can be attributed to the potential of GSO to improve metabolic efficiency. Similar findings have been reported in the literature, where supplementation with vegetable oils (Maenner et al., 2011) and antioxidants has shown positive effects not on appetite but on digestive and absorption processes (Chamorro et al., 2013; Abu Hafsa and Ibrahim, 2018).

Table 2. Effects of grape seed oil supplementation on growth performance of quails

Feed intake					
Days	Grape seed oil				P
	Control Mean±SEM	0.1% Mean±SEM	0.2% Mean±SEM	0.3% Mean±SEM	
1-7	4.65±0.12	4.60±0.08	4.77±0.13	4.72±0.08	0.664
8-14	11.78±0.48	11.17±0.18	11.25±0.17	11.85±0.37	0.365
15-21	20.98±0.11	20.87±0.48	21.15±0.27	21.62±0.18	0.330
22-28	22.86±0.21	22.14±0.22	22.96±0.45	22.85±0.36	0.305
29-35	24.78±0.41	24.73±0.45	24.18±0.32	24.68±0.14	0.598
1-35	17.01±1.56	16.71±1.56	16.87±1.55	17.14±1.57	0.998
Feed conversation ratio					
Days	Grape seed oil				P
	Control Mean±SEM	0.1% Mean±SEM	0.2% Mean±SEM	0.3% Mean±SEM	
1-7	1.72±0.038 ^a	1.57±0.04 ^b	1.67±0.03 ^{ab}	1.69±0.02 ^{ab}	0.032
8-14	3.14±0.13 ^a	2.89±0.07 ^{ab}	2.66±0.027 ^b	2.91±0.12 ^{ab}	0.022
15-21	3.50±0.01 ^a	3.14±0.05 ^b	3.03±0.05 ^b	3.17±0.02 ^b	0.001
22-28	4.22±0.03	4.02±0.03	4.20±0.09	4.16±0.08	0.179
29-35	5.64±0.26 ^a	4.59±0.12 ^b	4.69±0.16 ^b	4.85±0.17 ^b	0.005
1-35	3.64±0.27	3.25±0.21	3.25±0.22	3.35±0.22	0.590
Avera daily gain					
Days	Grape seed oil				P
	Control Mean±SEM	0.1% Mean±SEM	0.2% Mean±SEM	0.3% Mean±SEM	
1-7	2.69±0.027 ^b	2.93±0.06 ^a	2.86±0.09 ^{ab}	2.79±0.02 ^{ab}	0.048
8-14	3.75±0.00 ^b	3.87±0.06 ^b	4.22±0.04 ^a	4.09±0.05 ^a	0.000
15-21	5.99±0.03 ^c	6.65±0.08 ^b	6.98±0.06 ^a	6.82±0.06 ^{ab}	0.000
22-28	5.41±0.04	5.50±0.03	5.46±0.02	5.49±0.04	0.194
29-35	4.45±0.04 ^b	5.39±0.03 ^a	5.19±0.02 ^{ab}	5.12±0.04 ^{ab}	0.039
1-35	4.46±0.24	4.87±0.27	4.94±0.28	4.86±0.28	0.578

Different superscript letters (a–c) indicate statistically significant differences between groups ($p < 0.05$). SEM: Standard Error of the Mean

Regarding FCR, GSO supplementation resulted in significant differences during specific periods (Table 2). Particularly during days 1-7, the FCR value in the 0.1% GSO group was 1.57 ± 0.04 , which was statistically significantly lower than the control group (1.72 ± 0.038) ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, during the intervals of 8-14 days ($p < 0.05$), 15-21 days ($p < 0.05$), and 29-35 days ($p < 0.05$), FCR in the 0.1% and 0.2% GSO groups was significantly improved compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). However, no statistically significant difference was observed in FCR values throughout the entire period (1-35 days) ($p > 0.05$). The findings of this study reveal that low-level GSO supplementation (0.1% and 0.2%) improved FCR in quail and positively affected ADG during specific periods. The statistically significant increase in ADG in GSO-supplemented groups, particularly during the 8-21 day interval, supports the biological effects of GSO on growth performance. The finding reported by Abu Hafsa and Ibrahim (2018) that GS supplementation at a 20 g kg^{-1} level significantly improved FCR in broilers is

consistent with our study. This finding may be related to the positive effects of natural antioxidant compounds (phenolic substances, tocopherols, flavonoids) contained in GSO on intestinal health, nutrient absorption, and cellular metabolism (Gülcin, 2012; Abu Hafsa and Ibrahim, 2018; Gungor et al., 2021; Turcu et al., 2021). GSO, with its high linoleic acid and polyphenol content, is a functional component that can exhibit anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties (Gorinstein et al., 1994; Gungor et al., 2021). The use of GSO and essential oils in animal nutrition has been reported to potentially create indirect effects on performance through mechanisms such as maintaining intestinal mucosal integrity, regulating enzymatic activity, and reducing oxidative stress (Brenes and Roura, 2010; D'Eusanio et al., 2023). Furthermore, due to GSO's balancing effects on intestinal microflora, more effective digestion and absorption may have been achieved, particularly during the early growth period (Wu et al., 2019). The absence of statistically significant differences between groups during the 22-28 day period suggests that the effect of

GSO may have diminished over time or that the changing physiological needs of animals during the growth phase may have resulted in the suppression of this effect. This situation can be interpreted as the limited duration of antioxidant effects or adaptation mechanisms that develop over time in the organism may have balanced the effect of GSO (Abdel-Moneim et al., 2020; Mahfuz et al., 2021). In the study conducted by Vlaicu et al. (2017), the control group was compared with groups fed diets containing 2.5% GSO and 2.5% rosehip oil. Throughout the experimental period (days 14-42), no statistically significant difference was detected between groups in terms of FCR evaluation. Regarding ADG, GSO supplementation showed positive effects, particularly during early (1-7 days) and intermediate periods (8-21 days). At the end of the first 7 days, daily weight gain in the 0.1% GSO group was $2.93 \pm 0.06 \text{ g day}^{-1}$, which was significantly higher than the control group ($2.69 \pm 0.027 \text{ g day}^{-1}$) ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, during the 8-14 day and 15-21 day periods, ADG values in the 0.2% and 0.3% GSO groups were significantly higher compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$). However, no significant difference was found between groups during the 22-28 day and 1-35 day intervals ($p > 0.05$; Table 2). In this study, the effect of GSO supplementation on ADG in quail was distinctly positive, particularly during early (1-7 days) and intermediate (8-21 days) periods. The significant increase achieved with 0.1% GSO supplementation at the end of the first week suggests that the bioactive compounds contained in this oil (particularly tocopherols, flavonoids, and polyunsaturated fatty acids such as linoleic acid) play a supportive role in growth performance at an early age. These results are consistent with previous research, which has reported that plant oils with high antioxidant content can have positive effects on animal development (Eid, 2008; Tekeli et al., 2014; Bander, 2017). The ability of natural antioxidants to prevent diarrhea by reducing peristaltic movements in digestive disorders and protect intestinal mucosa against both oxidative stress and harmful microorganisms

can be considered one of the possible reasons for this effect (Kermauner and Laurenčič, 2008). The significantly higher ADG values in groups supplemented with 0.2% and 0.3% GSO compared to the control group during the 8-14 and 15-21 day periods of the experiment suggest that this effect may be dose-related. This situation can be interpreted as GSO potentially creating positive effects on intestinal health, thereby increasing nutrient absorption or supporting cellular metabolism to improve growth performance. Similarly, previous studies have emphasized that grape seed and its derivatives support growth performance in ruminant and monogastric animals (Juin et al., 2007), reduce oxidative stress (Wang et al., 2008), and improve feed utilization (Brenes et al., 2016). However, no significant difference was observed between groups in terms of ADG during either the 22-28 day period or the 1-35 day period, which encompassed the entire experimental duration. This finding suggests that the effect of GSO on growth is more pronounced, particularly during the early developmental period, but diminishes in subsequent weeks. The reason for this may be increased physiological adaptations in animals with advancing age, changes in fat metabolism, or the possible development of tolerance against GSO. Additionally, one possible explanation mentioned in the literature is that antioxidant effects may be more dominant during acute periods rather than chronic ones (Larsen, 2024). Tekeli et al. (2014) reported in their study that body weight gain was not increased. In a study conducted by Turcu et al. (2021), the comparison of two experimental groups supplemented with 1.5% and 3% GSO revealed that the group with higher GSO supplementation (3%) exhibited statistically significant average daily weight gain and total weight gain. It is observed that GSO supplementation positively affects the live weight gain of quail during early and intermediate growth periods, but this effect does not extend to the long term.

This situation highlights the importance of using GSO during the initial period to optimize growth performance and emphasizes the need

to determine the supplementation duration and level carefully.

Table 3. Effects of grape seed oil supplementation on cold carcass parameters of quails

	Grape seed oil				P
	Control Mean±SEM	0.1% Mean±SEM	0.2% Mean±SEM	0.3% Mean±SEM	
Live Weight	162.41±4.42	176.30±4.91	170.09±4.58	169.67±6.57	0.317
Carcass	108.94±3.12	120.79±2.75	113.73±3.01	115.88±4.17	0.095
Breast	41.94±1.17	45.13±1.43	43.60±1.51	43.76±1.76	0.515
Thigh	24.65±0.71	26.66±0.59	25.21±0.58	25.32±0.95	0.263
Wing	9.38±0.39	9.73±0.44	9.26±0.24	9.45±0.28	0.806
Back	31.55±1.35 ^b	38.38±1.06 ^a	35.32±1.25 ^{ab}	35.76±1.64 ^{ab}	0.007

Different superscript letters (a–c) indicate statistically significant differences between groups ($p < 0.05$).

SEM: Standard Error of the Mean

In terms of carcass parameters, although the 0.1% GSO group had the highest live weight and carcass weight, the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$; Table 3). However, significant differences were observed between groups in terms of back region weight, with the 0.1% GSO group showing the highest value (38.38 ± 1.06 g; $p < 0.05$). This suggests that polyphenol-derived oils may affect regional muscle development (Sanz et al., 1999; Obeidat et al., 2024). GSO contains high levels of linoleic acid, tocopherols, and phenolic compounds, particularly oligomeric proanthocyanidins. These compounds can protect cell membranes from oxidative damage by suppressing lipid peroxidation, thereby supporting muscle cell development (Shi et al., 2003). Indeed, in our study, a significant increase was observed in the 0.1% GSO group in terms of back region muscle development, which may indicate the selective effect of GSO on the development of localized muscle groups. Similarly, Tavárez et al. (2011) reported that the addition of natural

antioxidants to quail diets improved live weight gain and fattening performance. Botsoglou et al. (2004) demonstrated that phenolic antioxidants present in Apacox - a natural plant essential oil mixture added to diets - could positively affect carcass quality by reducing oxidative damage in muscle tissue. This effect is thought to result from antioxidants fighting free radicals in both systemic and local tissues, thereby promoting protein synthesis and muscle cell proliferation. Furthermore, the positive effects of polyunsaturated fatty acids contained in GSO on plasma lipid profile and cell membrane integrity may increase carcass yield by supporting endogenous anabolic processes (Pinchasov and Nir, 1992; El-Bahr et al., 2021). However, the lack of statistical significance in the increases in live weight and overall carcass weight suggests that this effect may occur at limited doses or in specific tissues. Therefore, future studies should investigate the effects of varying levels and durations of GSO on tissues in detail.

Table 4. Effects of grape seed oil supplementation on internal organ weights of quails

	Grape seed oil				P
	Control Mean±SEM	0.1% Mean±SEM	0.2% Mean±SEM	0.3% Mean±SEM	
Heart	1.4110±0.06 ^b	1.6815±0.06 ^a	1.4740±0.04 ^{ab}	1.4755±0.05 ^{ab}	0.007
Liver	3.77±0.28	4.376±0.32	4.427±0.36	3.985±0.34	0.445
Proventriculus	0.65±0.03	0.73±0.03	0.73±0.02	0.64±0.03	0.033
Gizzard	3.66±0.12	4.07±0.16	3.56±0.15	3.68±0.13	0.076
Entire intestine	5.20±0.29	5.86±0.36	5.58±0.39	5.47±0.28	0.575
Intra-abdominal fat	1.63±0.28	2.51±0.32	1.67±0.24	2.13±0.30	0.101

Different superscript letters (a–c) indicate statistically significant differences between groups ($p < 0.05$).

SEM: Standard Error of the Mean

GSO supplementation statistically affected some internal organ parameters (Table 4). Heart weight was found to be significantly higher in the 0.1% GSO group compared to the control group (1.6815 ± 0.06 g and 1.4110 ± 0.06 g, respectively; $p < 0.05$). Although the proventriculus weight also showed differences between groups ($p < 0.05$), this difference may have limited biological significance. No significant differences were found between groups in terms of liver, gizzard, intestine, and abdominal fat ratios ($p > 0.05$; Table 4). This supports the potential benefits of dietary polyphenols, particularly on the cardiovascular system. Grape seed oil is a natural source of antioxidants known for its rich polyphenol content. The endothelial function-improving and oxidative stress-reducing effects of flavonoids and proanthocyanidins on the circulatory system have been demonstrated in the literature (Sano et al., 2003; Terra et al., 2009). The increase in heart weight may be related to the positive effects of these compounds on myocardial cell functions. Additionally, some studies have shown that grape seed extracts may enhance cardiomyocyte proliferation and promote functional development by mitigating oxidative damage in cardiac muscle tissue (Bagchi et al., 2000). The change in proventriculus weight may be a reflection of direct or indirect effects of polyphenol supplementation on the digestive system. Some flavonoids have been shown to modulate gastric secretions and digestive enzymes (Haslam, 1996). However, since the biological significance of this increase is limited, additional physiological data are needed to evaluate whether it is directly related to digestive performance. The absence of significant differences in other internal organ weights and abdominal fat ratio suggests that GSO does not have a pronounced effect on the development of metabolic organs and lipogenesis. This indicates that the positive contribution of GSO to growth performance is more likely due to its oxidative balance-regulating effects. Indeed, some studies have reported that compounds with high antioxidant properties can improve performance without

reducing body fat accumulation (Botsoglou et al., 2004; Elejalde et al., 2024).

4. Conclusion

The data obtained in this study revealed that low-level GSO supplementation (0.1–0.2%) in quail diets improved FCR, increased ADG, and created positive effects on some carcass and internal organ parameters, particularly during early and intermediate growth periods. The natural antioxidant compounds contained in GSO are believed to be beneficial for intestinal health, nutrient absorption, and maintaining an optimal oxidative balance. These results demonstrate that the use of functional plant oils as feed additives in animal nutrition can improve performance criteria. However, the diminishing effect in subsequent periods necessitates careful planning of this additive in terms of duration and dose. This study has some limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the use of animals of both sexes may have introduced variability in the results due to sex-related physiological differences, potentially confounding the interpretation of treatment effects. Second, the absence of biochemical analysis of GSO limits our ability to identify which specific bioactive components were responsible for the observed outcomes. Future studies are recommended to investigate in detail the effects of different doses and longer-term GSO applications on growth performance, immune response, and meat quality.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

Ethical Committee Approval

This study was conducted with the approval of the Local Ethics Committee for Animal Experiments of the Siirt University

Experimental Animal Application and Research Center (Approval No: 2025/04/35).

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